

PHYTOREMEDIATION OF POST-MINING DISTURBED LAND

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ABSTRACT. Sustainable land application in post-mining areas is an essential ecological issue, connected with disturbed areas, pollution of heavy metals, etc. The current research studies opportunities for phytoremediation of lands disturbed by copper mining. Environmental state and soil conditions are examined. Analyses show that soils are weakly acidic, with a low concentration of total nitrogen, a very high concentration of K_2O and P_2O_5 , and arsenic above permissible values. The research determines phytostabilisation as a more reliable method for phytoremediation of disturbed lands in this case. The appropriate species for phytostabilisation have been studied. Based on the analysis of data, climate, and soil conditions, it is determined that tree species of four genera show the best ability for phytoremediation in this type of terrain: *Populus*, *Betula*, *Acer*, *Salix*. Afforestation schemes and possible methods for biomass treatment are proposed.

Keywords: copper mining, reclamation, phytoremediation, phytostabilisation

Introduction

Mining and mining waste management contamination of soils with heavy metals and metalloids (HMM) poses a serious risk to human health and the environment (Kostadinova et al., 2016; Todorova et al., 2019; Malinova et al., 2022) and thus provokes significant interest in developing technologies for their remediation, ecosystem restoration (Zukova – Aleksandrova and Mitkov 2019; Petrov, 2019), and sustainable use. Although there are many physical and chemical technologies proposed for the removal of HMM from soils, serious attention is paid to the possibility of phytoremediation due to the economic efficiency and environmental friendliness of the method.

Bioremediation uses the natural ability of some species of plants and microorganisms to extract, transform and inactivate HMM from the soil, based on the normal vital functions of organisms (Vasilev 2005; Bezlova 2016). Through their metabolic processes, plants and microorganisms use pollutants as a source of energy, and in most cases reduce their concentration to safe levels (Vasilev, 2005; Akhtar, 2013). For successful phytoremediation, the selected species must be tolerant to pollutants, must accumulate large amounts of biomass and finally - biomass at the end of the process should not be hazardous waste. The main phytotechnology used in the remediation of soils contaminated with HMM are phytoextraction, phytostabilisation, and phytoevaporation (Angelova et al., 2004; Vassilev, 2005; Emamverdian et al. 2018; Yadav et al., 2017, 2018).

In phytoextraction, plants remove heavy metals through their root system, accumulating them in their roots or transporting them to their aboveground parts (stems and leaves) (Cardwell et al. 2002; Kramer, 2005; Goolsby and Mason 2016; Emamverdian et al. 2018). Phytoextraction is a slow process of extracting heavy metals, applicable to soils with surface layer contamination and heavy metals that are not in high concentrations (Vasilev, 2005; Meyerholt 2013; Budzyńska et al., 2013).

In phytostabilisation, the contaminants are immobilised in the root system by absorption into the roots of the plants or by precipitation in the rhizosphere, reducing the mobility of

pollutants (Llugany 2012; Ali et al., 2013; Mani et al., 2013). Phytostabilisation has been developed as a technology based on the experience of restoring industrially damaged soils around old mines or metallurgical plants, which were often due to the high content of HMM and poor physicochemical characteristics of the soil, where vegetation is virtually absent (Chang et al., 2002; Fitz, 2002; Vasilev, 2005).

The present study aims to investigate the possibilities for phytoremediation of soils contaminated with heavy metals and metalloids because of past copper production, determine the appropriate method of phytoremediation, determine the appropriate species based on literature research and analysis of soils and environmental conditions in the area and prepare a plan for afforestation and application of amendments such as fertilizers.

Methods and materials

Study area

Soil samples were taken from sites contaminated because of mining activities in the Zlatitsa-Pirdop valley. This site will be used for forestry purposes after the reclamation. The study area is in forest areas at an altitude of 734 m. 6 sample subareas (SS) have been identified - sample subarea (SS) 1, SS 2, and SS 3 are industrial sites, and SS 4, SS 5, and SS 6 are old embankments because of past activities (Figure 1.).

Fig. 1. Part of the sample places

Materials

To achieve the objectives of the study, soil samples were taken from six sample areas - industrial sites and old embankments resulting from copper mining in the past. The sampling was performed according to standard BDS 17.4.5.01-85 "Nature protection. Soil. General requirements for sampling".

Methods

To determine the soil conditions, their physicochemical properties were studied. Soil reaction (pH) was measured potentiometrically following ISO 10390. The humus content was measured by Tyurin titrimetric (Tt) method. Total nitrogen in the soil was determined by the Kjeldahl method, assimilable forms of potassium and phosphorus - by the method of Petko Ivanov. The total content of Fe, Mn, Pb, Zn, Cu, Cd, As, and total S was determined by dissolving the samples in aqua regia followed by ICP-OES.

Results

Analysis of soil condition

According to the studies of soil samples (presented in Table 1), the soils are slightly alkaline and neutral.

Table 1. pH value and content of nutrients and humus

Sample subareas (SS)	SS 1	SS 2	SS 3	SS 4	SS 5	SS 6
pH	7.9	8.0	6.5	6.9	6.8	7.0

The value of pH is due to conducted methods of remediation of soils, involving liming. In SS 1 and SS 2 the soils are slightly alkaline. Under these conditions, alkaline earth carbonates are present in the soil, especially those of calcium. They are characterised by unfavourable conditions for plant nutrition due to the excess of basic cations and the lack of microelements. The soils in SS 3, SS 4, SS 5, and SS 6 have a neutral pH. They have a significantly lower amount of alkaline earth carbonates; nutrition is more balanced and has a prerequisite for optimal agrochemical mobility of soil elements (Malinova, 2010; Petrov, 2019). pH values are a prerequisite for the use of phosphorus fertilisers, as they are only applicable in alkaline environments.

In the studied samples, the fertility of the soils was determined by humus content and the content of total nitrogen, assimilable forms of phosphorus and potassium (Figure 2). Soil fertility is important for the further selection of tree species (Petrova et al., 2019; Petrov, 2019), as well as for determining the necessary ameliorants. The classification of soils by the content of nutrients and humus is made according to scale introduced by Penkov (1996). The analysed soils are characterised by a small nitrogen stockpile except for SS 2, in which a high stockpile is observed. In terms of humus content, the soils in the different sample areas vary from poor humus (SS 4), medium humus (SS 3, SS 5, SS 6), and rich humus (SS 1) to abundant humus (SS 2). According to the results of the analysis, fertilisation with nitrogen fertilisers should be envisaged, except for SS 2. In all samples, the content of assimilable forms of phosphorus is very high. Potassium reserves vary from very high (SS 4, SS 5) to very large (SS 1, SS 2, SS 3, SS 6).

The content of Fe, Mn, Pb, Zn, Ni, Cu, As, and total S were determined in the studied soils (Table 2 a, b).

a)

Fig. 2. Content of a) humus content and content of total nitrogen; (b) content of P₂O₅ and K₂O in soil samples

The calculated coefficients ($H_{MPC-pollutant}$) showing the exceedances of the maximum permissible concentrations (Order 3/2008) for the pollutants exceeding the norms are presented in Table 3.

Table 2. a) Concentration of Fe, Mn, total S, mg/kg

SS	Fe	Mn	S
	mg/kg		
SS 1	29397	391	10
SS 2	40037	397	4560
SS 3	26189	582	25751
SS 4	27923	395	12590
SS 5	29657	417	1174
SS 6	31034	429	1526

b) Concentration of Cu, Pb, Zn, Ni, Cd, As and their maximum permissible concentrations (Order 3/2008)

SS	Cu	Pb	Zn	Ni	Cd	As
	mg/kg					
SS 1	532	45	76	17	1	109
SS 2	1232	135	190	18	2	303
SS 3	714	56	116	8	1	102
SS 4	62	81	75	14	1	59
SS 5	249	106	79	14	1	42
SS 6	120	85	74	16	1	76
MPCs	500	500	600	25	10	40

According to the results, the iron content is below the average for soils in the country - 3.8% (Gyurov, 2015) except for PP 2. The manganese content falls in the range typical for soils - 200 -1000 mg/kg (Kabata-Pendias, 2011), but it is below the national average - 1000 mg/kg (Malinova, 2010). The content of Pb, Zn, Ni, and Cd does not exceed the MPCs for the respective element. The results of the soil samples show that most of the sample areas are lightly polluted (SS 4, SS 5, SS 6), moderately polluted (SS 1, SS 3) or dangerously contaminated with arsenic (SS 2), and practically unpolluted concerning copper (SS 4, SS 5, SS 6), slightly polluted (SS 1, SS 3) or moderately polluted (SS 2). The high levels of arsenic found in the studied samples are a prerequisite for impaired soil mineralisation and its ability to self-clean, and the development of vegetation, because of toxic effects on microbial flora (Kabata - Pendias, 2011; Yankova, 2016).

Table 3. Coefficients showing the exceedances of the MPC for arsenic and copper

Sample subareas	SS 1	SS 2	SS 3	SS 4	SS 5	SS 6
H _{MPC-As}	2.73	7.59	2.57	1.49	1.07	1.90
H _{MPC-Cu}	1.06	2.46	1.42	0.13	0.50	0.24

Soil analysis shows that phytoremediation is possible. They have a neutral pH, at which plant nutrition is close to balanced (Malinova, 2010). The studied soils are also rich in potassium and phosphorus, as well as well-stocked with humus. The content of copper in them is according to the permissible norms or exceeds the MPC up to 2 times. The content of arsenic suggests that methods should be sought for its removal or stabilisation in soils. Toxic levels (Penkov, 1996) of total S are reported.

Characteristics of the ecological condition of the region

The climate in the region is a temperate-continental climate (Sabev and Stanev, 1963), with mild winter and cooler summers. The northeast wind is predominant for the region - 25% on average for the year. The annual amount of precipitation is 617-618 mm. The snow cover lasts about 100 days. According to the Soil-geographical zoning of Bulgaria, the territory and the studied sites fall into the South Bulgarian xerothermal soil zone and the Mountain soil zone. Because of the little width in the studied area, we cannot talk about soil diversity in the area around the sample subareas, as this area has long been anthropogenically affected. In terms of floristics, the region falls within the floristic regions of Western Sredna Gora and Central Stara Planina according to the floristic zoning of the country. The natural vegetation is represented by pure and mixed oak, hornbeam, and beech forests (Serafimova et al., 2019).

Land use in the sample areas is mainly for forestry. Ecosystems are negatively affected by mining activities - many old embankments have been located. That is the reason for the change in vegetation. Black pine (*Pinus nigra*) and acacia (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) are also induced in the local flora during the reclamation of disturbed areas. Erosion was also found in the areas subject to sampling. In combination with the challenging natural type of restoration of vegetation, it threatens the protection and restoration of ecosystems

(Djingova et al., 1993; Bancheva-Preslavka, 2017, 2018, Zukova-Aleksandrova & Mitkov, 2018, 2019;).

Phytoremediation of the sample areas

Determination of phytoremediation method

Successful phytoremediation is a complex of interactions between soil, pollutant, and plants, and depends on several factors: the degree of soil contamination, the bioavailability of the pollutant(s), and the ability of plants to capture, absorb and accumulate the pollutant(s). In the present study, two approaches for phytoremediation of disturbed terrains are considered - phytoextraction and phytostabilisation. Phytoextraction is the most effective method of phytoremediation but does not apply to specific soil conditions. According to the literature, the method applies to soils with low concentrations of pollutants (Meyerholt, 2013), and as can be seen from the analysis of soil samples, the copper content exceeds 2 times the MPC and arsenic up to 7.6 times (SS 2). Another prerequisite for rejecting the method as applicable to the specific conditions is the possibility of the formation of a large amount of waste biomass with a high content of arsenic and the need to treat them as hazardous waste.

In soils contaminated with As and Cu phytostabilisation is a recommended method (Zhao et al. 2016; Yang et al. 2016), as the method results in a change in soil chemical composition induced by the presence of the plant itself and leads to immobilisation of pollutants in plant roots (Zhang et al., 2009).

Under specific soil conditions (hazardously contaminated with arsenic soils) phytostabilisation is also considered the more appropriate method. For successful remediation, the appropriate species for its implementation have been studied. The species are selected according to the requirements of the method (to select plant species with dense root systems to prevent leaching of pollutants (Singh, 2012), tolerant or resistant to pollutants - copper and arsenic, in this case, to have rapid growth and high biomass production, non-edible. Climatic and soil conditions in the area, natural vegetation, and land use in the areas around the test areas - namely as forest areas are also considered.

Selection of plant species

In the literature, several species have been reported as phytostabilisers applicable to specific climatic and soil conditions - the members of the family *Violaceae*, *Rhododendron tomentosum* and *Veronica beccabunga* (Bergqvist and Greger 2012), *Salix atrocinerea* (Otones et al., 2011), *Lupinus albus* et al., 2006), *Festuca rubra* (Radziemska et al., 2017), *Hypericum perforatum*, *Teucrium orientale*, *Phleum pratense* (Ghazaryan et al., 2018). For the application of this method, some authors believe that there are more appropriate tree plant species due to the large amount of biomass formed by the deep root system. Species of the *Salicaceae* family are used for this purpose. The combination between representatives of the genus *Salix* and *Populus* is suitable, such as *Populus nigra*, *P. alba*, *P. tremula*, *Populus euramericana*, *Salix alba*, *Salix purpurea*, *Salix caprea*. (Borgegard and Rydin, 1986; Punshon et al., 1995). Proven stabilisers of arsenic are members of the genus *Acer* - *A. pseudoplatanus* and *A. platanoides* (Budzyńska et al., 2019).

In the present case, the use of tree species is considered the better alternative due to the following arguments: i) land

use in the area - the sample areas are in forest areas; ii) high concentrations of pollutants - tree species would speed up the cleaning process due to the large amount of biomass they form, in the deep root system.

Based on the ecological characteristics of the area, the analysis of the condition of the soils in the studied areas, the location of the studied sites in forest areas, the purpose of their future use, and the literature review for phytoremediation of the studied sample areas it is appropriate to use the species: *Populus tremula* L., *Betula pendula* Roht., *Acer platanoides* L., *Salix alba* L. The characteristics of the species determine them as suitable for phytoremediation in the region, as they are naturally distributed in the region (Asyov et al., 2012) and are proven stabilisers of relevant pollutants. *Betula pendula* Roht is a tree species that accumulates a large amount of biomass, has a well-developed root system with well-developed lateral roots, can graze on extremely infertile soils; stabilises Cd> Mn> Zn> Pb> Cu> Ni> Fe. *Populus tremula* L. is a fast-growing tree species with great adaptability to soil conditions; stabilises Cd, Cu, Pb, Zn, Ni, and Cr. *Acer platanoides* L. is a tree species with a highly developed root system, tolerant to different soil types. It stabilises As, Cu, Pb, Tl, and Zn. *Salix alba* L is a fast-growing tree species with a large central root and strongly developed dense lateral roots that are not demanding to soil fertility, it stabilises As, Cd, Cu, Zn, Sb (Porter et al., 1975; Pajević et al., 2016).

Planting schemes of the species

It is envisaged that the average norm of saplings will be over 600 pieces/da due to unfavourable conditions because of high concentrations of arsenic in the soil. The planting schemes that are proposed assume optimal vegetation development and maximum results from the applied reclamation. Distance between individuals should be 0.65 m for *Populus tremula* L., and 0.80 m for the other species. The distance between the rows should be 1.30 m. They are presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Planting schemes

Appropriate ameliorants

Increasing the effectiveness of phytoremediation can be achieved through appropriate ameliorants. Soil analysis suggests the use of nitrogen fertilisers, as soils are poor in total nitrogen. It is recommended to apply ammonium nitrate twice after rainfall, in the spring immediately, and during the growing season, so that there are no losses, there is a longer-lasting effect, and to accelerate plant growth.

Fertiliser application rate is 7 kg/acre. The other necessary ameliorant is superphosphates. Phosphorus fertilisers are important for the faster rooting of plants and support their overall growth and development, and on the other hand, they

help neutralise arsenic in soils. It is recommended that they be imported in the autumn before phytoremediation. Fertiliser application rate is 11 kg/acre.

Treatment of generated biomass

Proper management of waste biomass resulting from phytoremediation is extremely important, as it poses a risk of re-contamination of the environment with heavy metals. Among the most widely used methods for biomass treatment are composting, incineration, pyrolysis, liquid extraction, energy use through combustion or gasification, biofuel production, or landfill (Šyc et al., 2016). The conditions described above do not suggest that the resulting biomass will contain arsenic and copper in increased amounts, as they will be stabilised in the rhizosphere. Studies show that the content of arsenic in the aboveground parts of the genus *Salix* is in the order of 1%. It was also found that the metalloid accumulates in the roots of wood species of the genus *Populus*, and less in their aboveground parts (Pajević et al., 2016).

Under these conditions, composting and compaction are good alternatives for the treatment of waste biomass, which has been reported by several authors (Kumar et al., 1995, Raskin et al., 1997, Garbisu et al., 2001). Composting can significantly reduce the volume of green waste, with the additional positive effect of reducing transportation costs to hazardous waste disposal facilities (Blaylock and Huang, 2000).

According to the Bulgarian legislation (Ordinance on separate collection of biowaste and treatment of biodegradable waste, in Art. 3 (1)), it is permissible "Composting on-site" of own biowaste in an amount not exceeding 10 m³/y compost, which is carried out directly from households and other sites, and the resulting compost is used at the place of formation only for own needs.

For the present case, it is recommended to collect waste biomass (leaves, branches, dried saplings) once a year. Before composting, the biomass must be tested for heavy metals and metalloids and pre-analysed for C and N content so that the amounts can be dosed correctly to achieve an optimal C/N ratio at the beginning of the composting process. According to a C/N ratio calculation, a recipe is made for the type and quantities of waste biomass to be placed in a bowl. Composting should be done in the following sequence: shredding of biomass, alternating spreading of fragmented branches, tops, leaves, etc. in a certain order in a layer 15 cm high, and laying a layer of fresh grass or other biowaste containing mainly nitrogen in a layer of 5 cm, forming a pile with dimensions - width 1.20 m, height 1-1.20 m, dew and periodic mechanical inversion - 3 to 5 times per week for the first 21 to 28 days and bowl height <1.3 m. The resulting compost needs to be sieved and its properties tested so that its future application can be determined.

Conclusion

As a result of the study of good practices for phytoremediation of soils contaminated with copper and arsenic and the analysis of soil samples, we can conclude that a phytoremediation is a possible approach to the restoration of these areas.

The soils have a neutral pH, medium stock of humus, and high content of phosphorus and potassium. The heavy metals and metalloids studied, except for arsenic, do not exceed the

MPC. Arsenic levels exceed the MPC, which makes phytostabilisation a more reliable method under specific conditions. Phytostabilisation is expected to lead to the immobilisation of the pollutant in the rhizosphere and reduce the possibility of generating waste biomass with hazardous properties.

The following plan has been developed for phytoremediation:

- Afforestation with four tree species known in the literature as phytostabilisers: *Populus tremula* L., *Betula pendula* Roht., *Acer platanoides* L., *Salix alba* L.

- Due to soil conditions (arsenic content above the MPC) it is recommended that the number of tree species should be over 600 per acre. Distance between individuals should be 0.65 m for *Populus tremula* L., and 0.80 m for the other species. The distance between the rows should be 1.30 m.

- The low nitrogen content determines the application of ammonium nitrate - twice in the spring before and during the growing season with a fertiliser application rate of 7 kg/acre.

- Before afforestation, it is planned to apply superphosphates with a fertiliser application rate of 11 kg/acre.

- It is recommended that the resulting biomass be composted on site.

It is important to note that phytostabilisation is not a technology for real cleaning of contaminated soils, but a successful strategy for stabilisation (inactivation) of TMM, which are potentially dangerous to humans and the environment. In situ inactivation of pollutants prevents their further spread and this reduces the impact on the site and adjacent ecosystems. Therefore, in the long run, the monitoring of pollutants is an integral part of the successful management scheme of phytostabilisation.

Afforestation of the selected species will take place in the spring of 2022. It is planned to sample the soil and the resulting biomass at the end of the growing season. A positive effect is expected to be reported after the third year.

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